

Open Letter

The Instigation of Astrotheology

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Introduction

For the sake of posterity and human interest, I thought I'd record my recollections of how I came to develop Astrotheology Theory. Astrotheology I, of course, the latest correct version of how the universe came to be and is sustained. It gives us the Structure of the Universe (an ellipsoid) and the Superforce. It gives us the Teflon Ether and a useful formula for energy, time, mass, and space. Also, we see how the human mind is calibrated to pick up on the signal that is the known universe.

I recall in High School at the almost all boys Catholic St Malachy's High School in the Uptown of Saint John, Canada, that my best teacher of all time, Mr Paul Assaff, UNB MA who taught us Enriched Math for 3 years put on the chalk board $x=1/(x-1)$. He called it the Golden Mean Parabola. It wasn't part of the lesson that day; just something he mentioned before beginning his lecture for the day. That parabola is the most important item in AT Math.

At the same high school, I was in conversation with a fellow student Robert Cyr. He told me that, from the enriched Chemistry he was taking from yet another great teacher, Dr Owen Dunn, that Scientists figured that they could not know the position and velocity of a particle at the same time. He also said when they look, they see what they expect to see. I asked Robert, what happened when they are equal? Robert said that is probably the answer to the problem. He asked, Dpo you mind if /I use that? I said No, I'm going to write a paper about it someday! Indeed, I did. It is AT Math.

In High School, Physics Teacher Joe Breen, who was a good teacher but a bad person, passed around a couple of magnets. We could feel the repulsion from the two magnets that relaxed when they were brought within a certain range of each other. That was important in developing Hook's law for the spring that is the universe. In Junior High School, Mr Collins emphasised that the formula for a spring is $F=-ks$. He made known to us that the negative sign is important. Indeed it is. He said he didn't know why the negative sign was there; only that it was. It was because the direction of the force is opposite the spring compression. In engineering at UNB, Dr John Dawe discussed the Hook's Law in a graph of the linear function. The modulus of elasticity I coined to be $cuz = \pi \cdot e = 3/14159265 \cdot 2.7182828 = 0.4233$. I had wondered as a teenager if subtracting two irrational numbers would yield a rational number. I believed that irrational numbers were impossible since the area of a circle is finite. $Area = \pi R^2$. I wondered about these things because I read books such as the Red Limit in the Astronomy Book Club when I was a teenager.

When I was enrolled at UNBSJ for Light and sound for Engineers, I recall the professor (whose name I forget) taught us that Kinetic Energy is

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always relative to something. I asked, where is the stationary point in the universe? He didn't answer either because he did not know or he didn't hear me. From this I realized that Einstein was wrong. I also know he was wrong because this idea I got from reading a physics textbook, that time would stop if all Kinetic Energy stopped. Therefore, the formula for time $= KE = 1/2 Mv^2$

At the university of Waterloo, I learned my greatest lesson even though I was only there for 4 months. It was from my Linear Algebra teacher. I forget his name. When I went to his office, he told me to drop the pencil and working black ink. Don't erase. Get a stack of white paper and start doing math research. He said, You don't have to meet every woman in the world before you decide which one you are going to marry! He was quite right. But I didn't hear him until I was 45 in 2012 when I began my investigation into AT Math.

Also at Waterloo, the same Math professor introduced us to the vector cross product. This is where the space equation came from $s = E \times t = |E||t|\sin t$ When space = time, $E = 1/\sin t = \csc t$ We also learned in Linear Algebra the eign vector, the eign value and the characteristic function.

Also at Waterloo, I had a Physics Professor who taught us that all things human follow the bell curve. It had nothing to do with Engineering, but everything to do with AT Math. The fame Pinko on the Price ios Right reminded me that the end slot that the disk ends up in is random. The slot thinks its drawing it. It isn't. It just plain luck. But statistics is telescopic. We have the central limits theorem which tells us that every measurement of the same thing falls into a bell curve. Cicil Engineers takes more statistics than Electrical or Mechanical.

I forget exactly when, but I do recall realizing one time I was sitting in the living room with my brother-in-law. I said, The function equals its derivative. $Y=y'$ Donnie had taken calculus three times. I took it twice. I failed it when I was at the University of Waterloo. Robert Cyr and I enrolled in Waterloo where we met our Waterloo. We didn't have calculus like the rest of the engineering students. They had grade 13; we had grade 12. We returned and enrolled in UNB.

We know from Physics that when the function equals its derivative, the velocity equals its acceleration. It kind of like walking up an escalator going down. I exclaimed to my brother In law, The function equals the derivative!

My interest lay in Architecture because I could draw. I applied to McGill Architecture but didn't gain acceptance. You need to have straight As ion first year engineering which I did despite begin there for only half the year. I went from Mechanical Engineering with an eye to Aeronautical Engi-

neering; Electrical which I thought was more math based; to Civil Engineering which had structures. The only “F” I got at UNB was in the main Electrical Engineering course. A Muslim, who thought I was trying to steal whom he thought was his girlfriend, poisoned me before the exam. I got a zero- did not write a number. I make too many mistakes to be a structural engineer. My grades ranged from D to A-. no consistency in grading and testing. (They really need standardized tests for Engineering as they do in the USA)

In Mechanical Engineering I had to take Light and Sould for Engineers; In electrical I had to take Differential Equations. Had I gone straight to Civil Engineering I would not have gotten these courses. (You’ve got to get the math when you are young, or you’ll never get it.) Also, the extra Electricity Circuits was valuable. Civil Engineers study Mechanics. It is the oldest of the Engineering subjects and most basic.

Also, at UNBSJ, I took psychology. IN basic Psych 1003, we learned that the human brain functions at 31.8Hz. I later realized that this is $1/\text{Pi}=0.318$. That was crucial to understand how the brain functions. When I went to a Grateful Dead concert, I took a hit of acid (LSD). I came to see the mind flickering. This grand error in judgement was a boon for me. (I don’t recommend taking any drugs.)

When doing AT Math calculations, I stumbled upon $1/81=0.012345679$. This is very important. Each decimal crest over to the next number on the scale. It is equal, to the Mass. The Gravitational constant comes from 7 of cycles of $(\text{Pi}-1)=6.67$. We also know that $M=\text{Ln } t$; or $MdM/dt=1/t=E$ We also realized that $\text{Force} = -Ma=\sin t$ and $P=Mv=\cos t$. From this we get the two pole solution.

When I was a boy laying in bed at night, I realized that the universe continues in circles. The only way to beat is is the break free from the circular time as a tangent. $X^2+y^2=R^2$ $x=y$ $x=1/\sqrt{2}=\sin 45=\cos 45$. I also noticed that nature, in my case water, don’t care where it goes. It just goes down hill. Humans care where we go, hopefully not Hell!

I began writing Astrology in January 2016. Since then I’ve published, with the help of generous journals, 1500 papers or an average of 4 per week for 7 years. I’ve never been paid a cent for all that work. I never tire. I could write another 1500 papers, but I’ve run out of material. I’m told I’m an Eminent Scientist and an eminent Medical Researcher. I suppose we’ll be adding Mathematical, Economics, Archaeologist, and Engineer. I don’t consider myself to be a scientist nor engineer. I’m a guy with a Bachelor of science in Engineering. I don’t have a Masters degree let alone a PhD. I wouldn’t pass a subject test for a PhD. A friend’s younger brother cursed me when we were kids that I wouldn’t rise above the bachelors level. Maybe some day, I’ll get an honourable doctorate which must be better from the other type, the dishonourable doctorate!

If I had had the cooperation from adults just getting what I earned, I would have accomplished a lot more. It is what it is.

I began putting pen to paper in January of 2016. I relied on the Bible that tells us that God’s spirit hovers over the water and that Man was made from Clay. The first few steps of Astrotheology were awkward. I didn’t truly hit my pace until after 700 written pages that I published in Paulymath (All my books are out of print and can’t be recovered. I had no sales after

years of trying).I know now that Astrotheology is the correct theory. How mush longer it will take to be discovered, I don’t know and really don’t care. They’ll did it up eventually. I know it is correct. Of course Einstein thought he was right as well, but he was mostly wrong.

The kicker is that this mathematical physics has been around since 4000 BC at least with the Minoans. The Jews believe the world began in 3760 BC. Moses, who likely had contact with the Minoans in 1450 BC, recorded it in Genesis and from there spread all around the world to the Maya in Mexico. Nothing new under the Sun.

I had only head mentioned the Ether. It was lucky that I called it that, the Teflon Ether. I used every one of the courses I took in Engineering at UNB, mainly UNB Saint John. (All you need is the 2 year diploma; not the 5 year degree.) I didn’t use as much from UNB Fredericton. Professors were not as good and classes were too big. Classes were too big at Waterloo as well. There weren’t enough seats there!

With the Ether comes light as a medium for light to travel through. Light is both a wave and a particle much like water waves. There is no need for Maxwell’s Equations. And the universe is not expanding; It is being compressed by the superforce. The Universe is an egg-shaped ellipsoid. Light is not bent by gravity as Einstein thought. It is passing through the voids in the Carbon tetrafluoride Teflon Ether. You get better results on the experience that proclaimed Einstein was right!

If you want to know how the universe works, dig up my 1500 papers. My memory is poor like Einstein, work hazard. The rest is History. This is how I came to develop the Theory called by me, Astrotheology. God left his fingerprints on the Universe. You don’t have to chose between belief in God and belief in science. That is the essence of my theory and what I hopple take away from it. As a gift from God, it was an awful lot of work. I plan to retire from what I’m doing; I’m going to get a job!

Biography

Paul T E Cusack was born on February 11, 1967, to parents Donald T and Eileen T (LeClair) Cusack in Saint John, New Brunswick, Canada. He studied at St. Peter’s Catholic School and St. Malachy’s Catholic School graduating with a High Honours Diploma. After a brief stint at the University of Waterloo in Mechanical Engineering, he went on to study Civil Engineering at the University of New Brunswick in Saint John and Fredericton. He graduated with a second-class honors degree in Civil Engineering in 1991. He went on to work as a Project Manager of large building construction projects in Ontario and obtained his professional licence in Engineering. After four years, there, he returned to the Maritimes and began studying human biology and the Bible. Next, he obtained a diploma in Urban Land Economics from the University of British Columbia graduating in 2005. He studied business informally including the MBA, CFA and Finance. Next, he wrote and self-published 37 titles at lulu.com in a variety of subjects. He published 17 blogs including one 4697 page one on Astrotheology- later made into a series of books. He also published several papers in Economics and in Human Biology, including “Sz and Its Causel. He is not married and has no children. His research interests expand to include every field in which universities teach. He believes a broad education is superior to a narrow one. His life motto is “If life gives you lemons, make lemonade” and “Make no small plans for they have no spark to ignite the heart of Man.”

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